

NFDI4Earth

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OneStop4All - Requirements and Concept Design

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Executive summary

Digital research products from the Earth System Sciences (ESS) are increasingly difficult to find, access, use, and share. There is a need for a platform that provides a coherent view on existing products, sources and information on how to use these and at the same time addresses specific needs of the ESS community. The OneStop4All addresses that gap and will function as the central access point to the NFDI4Earth services. Its content will be provided by and for NFDI4Earth members and the ESS community. This deliverable describes the approach to the requirements analysis and concept design of the OneStop4All as part of the software implementation process.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Requirements Engineering and Design Process for the OneStop4All	1
3	Larger Context - Gap Analysis	4
4	User scenarios	6
4.1	Discovery – Search for Information	6
4.2	Discovery – Browsing through Content	7
4.3	Discovery – Recommendation	7
4.4	Publishing	8
4.5	RDM Support – Question Answering	8
4.6	RDM Support – Software Reuse	9
4.7	New Information Products	9
5	Requirements from Gap Analysis and User Scenarios	10
5.1	High-level user experience requirements	10
5.2	High-level technical requirements	11
6	Mockups	12
7	Closing words	15
8	Acknowledgements	15

1 Introduction

Research products from and for the Earth System Sciences community are diverse and still difficult to find due to their distributed storage. User interfaces that provide access to distributed and linked resources are still lacking user-friendly functionalities to discover the data. The concept of the OneStop4All addresses these issues.

The OneStop4All is the primary visual and user-friendly access point to the NFDI4Earth services. It offers a coherent view on all relevant (distributed) research data management (RDM) resources provided by NFDI4Earth members and the Earth System Sciences (ESS) community, such as data repositories, software tools, education and training materials. It furthermore guides users through NFDI4Earth resources according to their specific ESS RDM and Data Science requirements and capabilities. The OneStop4All also fosters a seamless transition to a distributed user support network.

The OneStop4All will be designed iteratively, with the first version focusing on discovery and exploration. Here, we present the requirements and concept design, which have been developed by Measure 2.1 (M2.1) and Measure 4.3. (M4.3). A detailed description of the M2.1 work, with a particular focus on user needs and community engagement is published in a separate documentation¹.

2 Requirements Engineering and Design Process for the OneStop4All

The design of the OneStop4All follows a user-centred design approach to cope with the diverse user characteristics and requirements of the ESS community. Moreover, it is flexible enough to combine (1) usability engineering and user experience aspects with the (2) agile development of the NFDI4Earth-developed services and its regular self-assessments. This also allows the OneStop4All enhancement by integrating new NFDI4Earth-relevant services and information. The user-centred design process of the OneStop4All is inspired from the 11 steps of the (iterative) usability engineering model of Nielsen²³. The steps and their meaning in the context of the design of the OneStop4All are briefly introduced below. Though all steps are

¹ Anders, I., Hassler, S., Ryan, M., Thiemann, H. and Braesicke, P. (2024) 'NFDI4Earth OneStop4All Documentation' Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10955466>

² Nielsen, J. (1992) 'The usability engineering life cycle', *Computer*, 25(3), pp. 12–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/2.121503>.

³ Roth, R.E., Ross, K. and MacEachren, A. (2015) 'User-centered design for interactive maps: A case study in crime analysis', *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 4(1), pp. 262–301. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi4010262>.

listed below for the sake of completeness, a usability engineering effort, as Nielsen⁴ pointed out, can be successful without including every refinement and step. That is, the design of the OneStop4All will pick the steps most useful to NFDI4Earth, taking into account the project constraints (e.g., timelines and resources). Likewise, though the steps are presented in a linear order, in practice, design is iterative and hence the priority of the steps can be adapted to the project.

Step 0 - Consider the larger context

This step is about understanding the target user population and its tasks. To this end, we reviewed existing solutions with respect to the OneStop4All.

Step 1 - Know the user (led by M2.1)

This step is about establishing user profiles by assessing their needs and formulating use case scenarios. As of this writing, the first use case scenarios for the OneStop4All have been outlined. The scenarios were derived through brainstorming sessions within the NFDI4Earth consortium, interviews and a survey with selected stakeholders from the ESS community. They are briefly presented in sec. 4 "User scenarios".

Step 2 - Competitive Analysis (led by M2.1)

This step is about critically comparing technical solutions which accommodate similar, relevant use cases and assessing how a OneStop4All based on them could fulfil our users' needs. We conducted an evaluation of existing user interface solutions, notably solutions by other consortia and international/European solutions in the ESS. We also evaluated existing technical solutions.

Step 3 - Formulate Requirements (led by M4.3)

This step is about using insight from the needs assessment and competitive analysis to formalise a requirements document of proposed functionality to guide design and development. The formulation of usability goals for the OneStop4All as suggested by Nielsen is ongoing.

Step 4 - Participatory Design

This step focuses on recruiting a representative set of target users to participate in the conceptual design of the interface. The necessity of this step and the extent to which it can be implemented will be assessed in the course of the NFDI4Earth project.

Step 5 - Coordinated Design

This step is about coordinating designs across the project team to develop a consistent look and feel (i.e., product identity) for the OneStop4All, the Living Handbook, the EduTrain, and the

⁴ Nielsen, J. (1992) 'The usability engineering life cycle', *Computer*, 25(3), pp. 12–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/2.121503>.

User Support Network. This task is currently ongoing.

Step 6 - Guidelines and Heuristic Analysis

This step is about recruiting experts during design and development to evaluate the OneStop4All interface according to guidelines and heuristics. The necessity and value of this step will be assessed during the course of the NFDI4Earth project.

Step 7 - Prototyping (Joint work between M2.1, M4.3, 52°North and Pikobytes)

This step is about creating prototypes (e.g., interactive mockups, partially-functional prototype, fully-functional prototype) of the OneStop4All. As of this writing, a first version of the mockups was implemented. This is shown in sec. 6 “Mockups” .

Step 8 - Empirical Testing

This step is about recruiting a representative set of target users to evaluate the utility and usability of the prototypes during their evolution. The task is planned.

Step 9 - Iterative Design

This step is about revising the prototype (i.e., the OneStop4All interface) based on the feedback from guidelines/heuristic analysis and/or the empirical testing. The task is ongoing.

Step 10 - Feedback from Production Use

This step is about acquiring user feedback about the OneStop4All interface after it has been deployed to production to inform future product releases. The task is planned.

The focus of this report is on the requirements and the concept design for the OneStop4All. The methodical process to build the OneStop4All was introduced above. The remainder of the report focuses on the preliminary outcomes for:

- Step 0 – Larger context: We reviewed existing solutions regarding the OneStop4All to identify current gaps.
- Step 1 – Know the user: In the current report, we present only some scenarios to give an idea about the functionalities of the OneStop4All. We use a combination of *problem and activity scenarios*⁵ to communicate the vision for the OneStop4All, and hence its concept and functional requirements.
- Step 3 – Formulate requirements: Some examples of functional requirements can be seen in the scenarios. To these, we briefly add high-level user requirements and high-level technical requirements that are identified at the moment of this writing.
- Step 7 – Mockups: We present examples of mockups of the OneStop4All as of July 2023. .

⁵ Rosson, M.B. and Carroll, J.M. (2002) ‘Scenario-based design’, in J. Jacko and A. Sears (eds) *The Human-Computer Interaction Handbook: Fundamentals, Evolving Technologies and Emerging Applications*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, pp. 1032–1050.

Given the focus of this deliverable on requirement analysis and the concept design for the OneStop4All, the documentation of the outcomes for the first steps is done. Ongoing activities (Step 5), planned activities (Steps 8-10) and steps whose inclusion is still under assessment (Steps 4 and 6) will be presented together with the results of the next iterations for steps 0, 1, 3, and 7 in subsequent deliverables.

3 Larger Context - Gap Analysis

NFDI4Earth builds upon an extensive list of existing services and digital research products. The task areas 2 and 3 therefore conducted a detailed review for services and portals. Within NFDI4Earth, we develop approaches along general use cases, that stem from key areas in which researchers still need assistance. The use cases include (the references next to a general use case hint at the needs, explicitly or implicitly):

- Discovery⁶⁷⁸: find resources (e.g., datasets, software/tools, publications) relevant to their current research tasks.
- Publishing⁹¹⁰: find appropriate metadata standards and repositories to publish their research information products.
- RDM Support¹¹: obtain help when they are stuck on tasks related to research data management.
- New information products¹²¹³: create and share information products (e.g., visualisations, analysis results) based on existing ones (e.g., datasets).

⁶ Bernard, L., Mäs, S., Müller, M., Henzen, C. and Brauner, J. (2014) 'Scientific geodata infrastructures: challenges, approaches and directions', *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 7(7), pp. 613–633.

⁷ Degbelo, A. (2020) 'Open data user needs: a preliminary synthesis', in A.E.F. Seghrouchni, G. Sukthankar, T.-Y. Liu, and M. van Steen (eds) *Companion Proceedings of the Web Conference 2020*. Taipei, Taiwan: ACM, pp. 834–839.

⁸ Thanos, C. (2013) 'A Vision for Global Research Data Infrastructures', *Data Science Journal*, 12(0), pp. 71–90.

⁹ Bernard, L., Mäs, S., Müller, M., Henzen, C. and Brauner, J. (2014) 'Scientific geodata infrastructures: challenges, approaches and directions', *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 7(7), pp. 613–633.

¹⁰ Stall, S., Yarmey, L., Cutcher-Gershenfeld, J., Hanson, B., Lehnert, K., Nosek, B., Parsons, M., Robinson, E. and Wyborn, L. (2019) 'Make scientific data FAIR', *Nature*, 570(7759), pp. 27–29.

¹¹ Degbelo, A. (2020) 'Open data user needs: a preliminary synthesis', in A.E.F. Seghrouchni, G. Sukthankar, T.-Y. Liu, and M. van Steen (eds) *Companion Proceedings of the Web Conference 2020*. Taipei, Taiwan: ACM, pp. 834–839.

¹² Bernard, L., Mäs, S., Müller, M., Henzen, C. and Brauner, J. (2014) 'Scientific geodata infrastructures: challenges, approaches and directions', *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 7(7), pp. 613–633.

¹³ Thanos, C. (2013) 'A Vision for Global Research Data Infrastructures', *Data Science Journal*, 12(0), pp. 71–90.

With respect to the results of the landscape analysis and these use cases, we identified the following problems as relevant for the OneStop4All concept:

- Digital research products from the Earth System Sciences (ESS) community are diverse and increasingly difficult to find and access, e.g., re3data provides metadata for more than 30 ESS repositories hosted in Germany¹⁴; the EOSC Marketplace provides metadata for more than 200 ESS services¹⁵; and more than 90 services are provided by NFDI4Earth members and partly described in the previously mentioned registries.
- ESS-specific research questions require integrative approaches across resource types, e.g., by combining data or linking metadata about the different resources. However, existing platforms do not fully support that as they typically focus on one type, e.g., on datasets.
- Research data management problems in ESS need to consider different user needs, (sub) disciplinary aspects, and technologies. There is no platform that provides access to (distributed) best practices, descriptions to solve these RDM problems and ESS helpdesks.
- Data publication and curation are complex and the related tasks, from data preparation to repository selection, are often underestimated by the data providers or lack discipline-specific support.

¹⁴ <https://www.re3data.org/search?query=earth%20system%20sciences&countries%5B%5D=DEU>

¹⁵ https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?object_id=&type=&anchor=&sort=_score&q=earth+system+sciences

4 User scenarios

Scenario-based design¹⁶ is an approach for requirement analysis and concept design that understands requirements as statements on envisioned usage situations. Scenarios describe such situations considering the motivations and characteristics of users and the user interactions with the envisioned software, in our case the OneStop4All. The scenario-based design approach therefore helps us to keep the strong focus on usability / user experience from the beginning of the software development process. Moreover, it allows for an iterative approach by adding additional scenarios resulting in new OneStop4All functionalities at later project stages. In this section, we describe future scenarios covering those that will be covered in the first and in later OneStop4All versions.

4.1 Discovery – Search for Information

Note: the scenario below uses data repositories as an example of a resource being searched for, but the workflow presented is intended to be reused for other types of resources that will be made searchable through the OneStop4All: datasets, software, organisations, vocabularies, web services, standards, scientific articles and virtual research environments.

Jemal, an Earth System Science researcher, has just finished collecting a geospatial dataset for his latest project. He is now looking for a data repository to publish this dataset according to the FAIR principles. He is familiar with re3data as a valuable source, yet, misses some useful information about the repositories returned by a search in that platform (e.g., whether or not the repositories are still maintained, their spatial/temporal coverages). Most importantly, repositories of regional scope seem not to be included. His search for “remote sensing nrw” returns no results. He turns to the OneStop4All operated by NFDI4Earth and tries the same query. He gets an overview of repositories with regional scope fitting his query. The list also includes geoportals of urban scope. He can refine his search parameters via a faceted navigation and retrieve structured information about the repositories shown. He can see that some of these repositories are tagged with the NFDI4Earth Label, so he selects one of these for further inspection. Scrolling through the details about this repository, he notices one unexpected feature: there is a section “Related Resources” showing information about related resources to the current repositories, available in the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub. He can see datasets published by NFDI4Earth members already published in a given repository. That increases his confidence on the relevance of the repository for his purpose. The OneStop4All offers a visualisation of the connection between these related entities as a graph. The spatial coverage of the repository is also visualised on a map.

¹⁶ Carroll, J. M., Rosson, M. B., Chin, G., & Koenemann, J. (1998): Requirements Development in Scenario-based Design. IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 24(12), 1156-1170.

Key features:

- Overview of available resources in the Earth System Sciences
- Search through resources spread across repositories and the Web
- Display of structured information about these resources
- Faceted navigation (e.g., filter by spatio/temporal properties of the resources)
- Information about linked resources (e.g., organisations) to a given type of resource (e.g., repository)
- Visualisation of the links between resources as a graph
- Visualisation of the spatial context of georeferenced resources on maps

4.2 Discovery – Browsing through Content

No specific scenario is needed for this: the OneStop4All takes much of its inspiration from re3data (<https://www.re3data.org/browse/>) and offers the possibility of browsing by subject, by content type and by country. Here, we envision to design interactive visualisations for multi-dimensional filtering (e.g., filter by subject and content type simultaneously), which is not fully covered by one of the current platforms alone.

4.3 Discovery – Recommendation

Mary is looking for a dataset similar to her current one from different locations in order to combine them in her analysis. Searching the Web manually for these datasets appears cumbersome. Also, she would not know where to start. Mary recalls at this point that the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All offers a recommendation function. “Let me try this out”, she says. The menu offers three options: *manual* (enter metadata about their dataset manually), *DOI* (have the metadata extracted automatically based on the dataset’s DOI), and *upload* (have the metadata extracted automatically based on the content of the dataset). She goes for the DOI-based option and paste the DOI of their dataset into the appropriate field. The metadata about the dataset is quickly extracted and she is asked for confirmation. After validating that the information extracted is correct, Mary receives suggestions of similar datasets to hers from the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub along with the corresponding similarity scores. Mary also has the possibility of configuring how the similarity score is computed. She can change the weights for spatial, temporal and thematic similarity. She can also change the properties to include in the computation of the respective similarity scores: spatial similarity (e.g., spatial distance, shape similarity between geometries, similarity of attribute properties of spatial regions), temporal similarity (e.g., temporal distance, temporal duration), thematic similarity

(e.g., keywords, description, title). She is excited about the wealth of data available and the configuration options from the OneStop4All user interface.

Key features:

- Manual metadata provision about spatial/temporal/thematic properties of datasets
- Semi-automatic metadata extraction about the spatial/temporal/thematic properties of datasets, based on either a DOI or the content
- Similarity search, based on a meaningful computation of similarity between datasets
- Flexible configuration of the parameters to include in the similarity computation and their weights

4.4 Publishing

In the first version, we do not support publishing of datasets through the OneStop4All, but only finding the right repository to publish a given dataset. For finding, see sec. 4.1 on “Discovery – Search for Information”.

4.5 RDM Support – Question Answering

Paulo is looking for guidelines about how what it means to make his data/publication/software FAIR. A search using his usual search engine returned several links to click through. “I’m not looking for websites, I am looking for an answer”, he sighs, but then goes on clicking through the list of websites returned. One of them has NFDI4Earth in the title, and he clicks on it. He was indeed aiming at making a dataset produced in the context of an Earth System Sciences research project FAIR. Following this link leads him to the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All, and he immediately sees a list of results displayed as results of the search “Making Data FAIR”. The results are of two types: Educational Material and Living Handbook articles. He also sees, next to these, a highlighting of Bot4Earth, a Chatbot in a beta version about “Question Answering”. He goes for the latter and types in the question “How to make my ESS data FAIR”. Bot4Earth returns a series of meaningful steps, and a hint that he can learn more through some resources available in the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub. For these, he should type “Making Data FAIR” in the search field. He now makes the connection: Bot4Earth only provides general information about the steps to more FAIR data, detailed information can be found in the Educational Material and Living Handbook articles. So, he goes for the bot’s suggestion. He then selects the Living Handbook article with the title “FAIR ESS Data 101”. Using a simple geographic dataset as an example, this Living Handbook article walks him through the steps to a FAIR dataset. In addition, links to materials or info boxes are displayed in each step, which briefly explain individual aspects and basics. Examples of repositories are also mentioned where he can publish data FAIRly.

Furthermore, he learns something about licenses and quickly finds out which license he needs for his data. Paulo smiles. He finally understood within 10 minutes what the FAIR principles are all about.

Key features:

- A bot for general information about questions related to research data management
- The bot redirects to the Educational Material and Living Handbook articles related to learn deeper about a given subject

4.6 RDM Support – Software Reuse

Paulo is navigating through the OneStop4All and sees a section on “Software Marketplace”. He is curious to see the resources available in that section and launches a search about the topic of data cubes. His search returns a list of tools from the NFDI4Earth community helping to visualise and/or analyse data cubes. In the “Related Resources” section of the tools’ descriptions, he sees two types of resources from the Knowledge Hub related to the software he is currently inspecting: datasets from the Knowledge Hub already visualised with the current tool and a Living Handbook article about the tool. He is curious to know more and clicks on the link of the Living Handbook article. He is redirected to a page, where he finds an interactive tutorial, with worked examples about the use of the tool. The Living Handbook article also provides simple and clear instructions about how to download/install the tool on his machine.

Key features:

- Dedicated section of the OneStop4All for tools
- Recommendation of Living Handbook articles related to a (software) tool as our first step to facilitate/promote software reuse
- Smooth transition between the OneStop4All and the Living Handbook article (and back)

4.7 New Information Products

Mary is currently writing an essay on the evolution of the demographics of Germany in the past 20 years. She navigates the OneStop4All and uses its search interface to find related datasets. A few clicks and she is done - she has found a relevant dataset for her essay. She is now interested in visualising the dataset as a map to better understand the nuances of demographic changes across the geographic regions. Unfortunately, she is only at the beginning of her studies and not yet skilled in using geographic information systems (GIS). *Fortuitously*, she sees “Visualise your dataset as a map” as an action button next to the detailed description of the dataset. She is curious to see what it offers and clicks on the button. A web-based interface visualises the

dataset as a map, with an option to navigate through the different years. She is excited! She then plays around with the different diagrams and customisation options available and after 10 mins, she has explored the dataset enough to get back to her essay. She realises that she can save and share her latest configuration as a persistent URL. “This is awesome”, she exclaims; “I can make my work even more reproducible with NFDI4Earth”. She takes screenshots of her final map, and adds the persistent URL as an online reference to her essay. The OneStop4All has saved her day.

Key features:

- Connection of datasets with relevant services for their visualisation and analysis
- Sharing of the result of the visualisation or the analysis as a new information artefact (web-based or not)

5 Requirements from Gap Analysis and User Scenarios

The previous section has provided examples of functionalities offered by the OneStop4All, based on the description of issues currently faced by users, and user activities envisioned in the context of the OneStop4All. This section now makes the information collected into a first proper version of a list of requirements. We provide separate tables on high-level user experience requirements on the one hand, and high-level technical requirements on the other hand.

5.1 High-level user experience requirements

The OneStop4All is the primary access point for the ESS community to discover and explore relevant ESS resources and should therefore respond to the following high-level user experience requirements:

Table 1: High-level user experience requirements for the OneStop4All

Category	Main requirements
General usability and user experience	<p>Follow general usability and user experience guidelines for Web applications with particular respect to discovery and exploration. That includes for instance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shneiderman’s mantra¹⁷: Overview first, zoom and filter, then details-on-demand • Nielsen’s: 10 Usability Heuristics for User Interface Design¹⁸

Category	Main requirements
Resource discovery	<p>Enable user-friendly, easy discovery and access of relevant ESS resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide useful search and filter functionality for the given metadata and data so that users can select resources that best fit their requirements • Offer a problem-oriented navigation concept to guide the users • Provide a coherent and structured overview on metadata for a resource and information on linked resources • Provide action items to easily access related resources or the data source • Allow easy identification of NFDI4Earth labelled services
Resource access	<p>Enable user-friendly, easy access to relevant ESS resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer easy access to data and services, e.g., via harmonised metadata • Allow easy and user-friendly access to Living Handbook articles and navigation through the article • Provide access to a helpdesk
Resource publication	<p>Support users in finding repositories and metadata standards to easily complete publication Offer means of identifying the most relevant portal in the ESS to publish a given resource</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggest metadata standards relevant to the publication of a given resource, based on its description

5.2 High-level technical requirements

The OneStop4All is embedded in the application layer of the NFDI4Earth software architecture and should therefore address the following high-level technical requirements:

¹⁷ Shneiderman, B. (1996): The Eyes Have It: A Task by Data Type Taxonomy for Information Visualizations. Proceedings of the 1996 IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages, 336-43. VL '96. Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society.

¹⁸ Nielsen, J. (1994a): Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. Proc. ACM CHI'94 Conf. (Boston, MA, April 24-28), 152-158.

Table 2: High-level technical requirements for the OneStop4All

Category	Main requirements
General software development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow the NFDI4Earth software architecture constraints, e.g., uses an established programming language and is provided as Free and Open Source (FOSS)
Linking to NFDI4Earth-developed services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub as central metadata and data source via API Provide a comprehensive user interface for the Living Handbook Link to the EduTrain learning management system and shows information on training materials based on their metadata stored in the Knowledge Hub
Future extensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate a form to contact the User Support Network Allow for the integration of future and existing services, e.g., visualisation services Allow for the presentation of new/updated resource types from the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub Allow for the integration of NFDI base services whenever possible, e.g., IAM service

6 Mockups

Mockups were built as preliminary step for the implementation. As the NFDI4Earth ontology and the Knowledge Hub are still under development, the mockups show the structure of the OneStop4All pages, but do not cover all details, e.g., all metadata for a specific resource type.

The first version of the OneStopAll is designed with five main sections focusing on discovery and exploration as well as footer and header. The sections include 1) a prominent search bar for discovery of all provided resources, e.g., metadata and data; 2) an entry point to overview articles on relevant ESS-specific RDM topics; 3) a resource section to get information for resources filtered for a specific resource type; 4) an interactive graph-based visualisation to learn about the linkages of resources and topics; and 5) a section with information on how to participate in NFDI4Earth see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Structure of the OneStop4All homepage. The footer is removed due to space limits.

Figure 2: Structure of the result list page with a central search bar and an interactive section for applied filters below. The result list visually structures the results. Different templates allow to show proper information for each resource type, e.g., type, name, authors and publication date for articles.

The search result list covers basic information for the resources, facets for filtering in particular for spatial and temporal filter as well as navigation items, for example for paging (Fig. 2). The central search bar is designed and placed on the OneStop4All homepage. Below the search bar, the page is organised in two columns. The left column contains the applied filters and the results. We designed a result template for each resource type. All templates include the resource type and the name of the resource.

Facet filters are displayed in the right column. The facet filters will be deactivated, if results don't provide information for the facet, e.g., the map filter will be deactivated, if spatial information are missing.

7 Closing words

This deliverable has introduced a preliminary list of requirements for the OneStop4All, based on a review of the literature and of existing solutions, as well as inputs from the interaction with users (e.g. workshops). The requirements identified and the overall OneStop4All concept are currently being refined using the usability engineering life cycle as a framework.

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